

Women in Vishwa Guru Bharat

Kumari Pooja Anand

Research Scholar, Patliputra University

Orcid id: - <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-6391-3223>

ABSTRACT: Vishwaguru Bharat is the vision of India being a teacher that inspires the world with its culture and holistic development. A key component of this vision is acknowledging women as playing a central role in India's socio-economic and cultural development. Despite their immense historical roles, women's contributions have frequently been overlooked.

This paper signifies how the status of women evolved from ancient to modern India, with Gargi and Rani Lakshmi Bai of Jhansi being a few of the scholars and leaders who guided history through their intelligence and bravery. One of the most important tools of empowerment is education that has improved after independence, through schemes like the Right to Education Act and "Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao", which has made women develop more in various sectors.

Women have been entering politics in increasing numbers, the best-known examples being Indira Gandhi and Mamata Banerjee. The Women's Reservation Bill is an attempt to expand this inclusivity. They are also economically women lend a lot of time, energy and money to households and enterprises through programs on micro-credit. They also promote and preserve India's cultural heritage globally.

But problems of the gender gap and social subjugation still exist that will need to be addressed through policy reforms and changes in attending Vishwaguru Bharat. India, by embracing inclusion and fairness, can ascend to its place in the world and propel the world.

KEYWORDS: Gender Equality, Socio-Economic Development, Vishwaguru Bharat, Women's Empowerment, Women's Education in India, Women's Political Participation.

INTRODUCTION

The notion of the Vishwaguru Bharat organization reflects the desire of India to become the leader all over the world in the spheres of education, culture, and economic development. This vision that stems from the ancient knowledge and cultural history of India's tradition is not only a tribute to the past but a map towards the future. At the center of this grand plan is the status and role of women in society, which is considered and encouraged to be more proactive. Indian women have always played a major role in the country's progress and have made immense contributions to areas like education, politics, economy, and social culture of the country. But their experiences remain neglected or ignored mainly and hence the need for a keen examination of their exposition and roles.

In the earlier times of the Vedic culture, women like Gargi and Maitreyi who participated in intellectual and philosophic discourses are clear evidence of the respected status women enjoyed in ancient India (Sharma, 1991), Again from history women from the ancient Indian civilization like the well-learned Mariska, royal envoys like Arundathi and Surpanaka. These women were not only acting in this discourse but were actively creating the mother and the intellectual and spiritual aspects of the discourse of their era. There are many Indian women who, in the medieval period, gave wonderful performances that show how powerful and daring they were and how they overcame gender discrimination. Indian women played an important role in shaping the political and military future of India (Cleve & Forbes, 2005).

Women's position and functioning in the present world have changed and become more diverse and multifaceted, corresponding to the general tendencies. After independence, there was a dramatic change in the social outlook, especially in female education and equality. Some of the most important policies include the Right to Education Act of 2009 and the "Beti Bachoo Beti Padhao" scheme, which has seen women's literacy levels shooting up and women being encouraged to go to school (Mukherjee, 2014). In this context, claims efforts highlight the significance of women's education in the attainment of socio-economic development and the creation of a rational society.

Another highly significant change in women's rights is their active involvement in politics, which was initiated by the first female PM of India – Mrs. Indira Gandhi. Sushma Swaraj, Mamata Banerjee, and many other female politicians are currently figuring out

the future and direction of politics in India (Kishwar, 1996). The government's Women's Reservation Bill, which has not yet been passed into legislation but seeks to provide a 33% share of women in the Parliament and state assemblies, is a big stride in as much as it concerns the enhancement of minority representation (Ghosh, 2009).

In the economic activity, women have also gained standing, especially in the informal sector economic activity. They play significant roles in agricultural settings, small-scale industries, and handicrafts, but they are confined to an informal employment base, and most of the time, they are not rated or valued properly (Mazumdar, 2004). Some of the notable programs that have dynamically impacted the economic status of women include the Self-Help Group (SHG) movement and microfinancing schemes popular in today's world that have given women a chance to go into business on their own (Pitt et al., 2006). To this end, this economic empowerment is central to the actualization of the development of this nation.

In terms of custom and culture, the women of India have given the society their heritage and also brought about transformations within the society by encompassing themselves within the realm of writers, artists, poets, musicians, dancers, and singers, among many other professionals. Self-fashioning and the role of the writer as an artist are also seen in contemporary women literary figures, Arundhati Roy and Anita Desai, who have taken Indian culture to the global theatre (Dhawan, 2005). The assessment of these three works reveals how female characters are actively involved in both maintaining and altering localized culture and customs, which contributes to the complexity and development of Indian society.

However, the situation of women in India is not very favorable as they still experience employment discrimination, violence, and restricted resource access. To solve such problems, rational, effective policies have to be worked out, and society has to be altered (Desai & Thakkar 2001). Gender equality remains one of the most significant issues of concern in the contemporary world; therefore, education for women, changes in laws and policies, and women's economic rights are crucial for the establishment of women's equality in all domains.

HISTORICAL CONTEXT

Historically, women in India have been instrumental in various fields, leaving an indelible mark on the nation's sociocultural and intellectual landscape. In ancient times, the Vedic period is particularly noteworthy for the prominent roles played by women such as Gargi and Maitreyi. Gargi Vachaknavi, renowned for her profound knowledge and philosophical acumen, participated in debates with eminent scholars like Yagvalkya, challenging them on metaphysical concepts and the nature of existence (Sharma, 1991). Similarly, Maitreyi, a philosopher and wife of sage Yagvalkya, is celebrated for her contributions to the philosophical discourses in the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad, where she delves into the intricacies of the soul and ultimate truth (Sharma, 1991). These women were not only scholars but also advisors and philosophers, significantly enriching the intellectual and cultural fabric of ancient India. The medieval period further underscores the pivotal roles of women as leaders and warriors, often defying the patriarchal constraints of their times. Rani Lakshmi Bai of Jhansi, for instance, remains an iconic figure in Indian history. Her leadership during the Indian Rebellion of 1857 exemplifies unparalleled bravery and strategic acumen. Lakshmi Bai's resistance against British colonial forces is a testament to her commitment to sovereignty and justice, symbolizing the spirit of resistance and resilience (Forbes, 2005). Razia Sultana, the first and only female ruler of the Delhi Sultanate, also stands out for her administrative prowess and military leadership. Ascending the throne in 1236, Razia Sultana challenged gender norms by donning male attire and leading her armies into battle, asserting her authority in a male-dominated milieu (Forbes, 2005). Her reign, though short-lived, demonstrated that women could govern with equal if not superior effectiveness and vision.

The given historical narratives reveal that Indian women have been very courageous and possessed leadership qualities – the qualities important for the conception and building of the country. In the past, the status quo was intensely rigid, yet women like Gargi, Maitreyi, Razia Sultana, and Rani Lakshmi Bai paved the way for women leaders to come into their own. They cannot be excluded from the process of conceiving India's complete profile and are essential for the country to imagine a ride to world leadership and fellowship.

WOMEN IN EDUCATION

An important domain that has seen a drastic change is the participation of women, particularly in the aspect of education in India, after independence. The status of women's education has changed for the better as it has experienced a gradual steep growth from a meager 8%. While the Asian literacy rate was a meager 6% in 1951, it has escalated to 65.46% in 2011 (Government of India, 2011).

This significant improvement in female literacy plays a significant role in increasing women's employment opportunities and transforming them into agents of change.

One can observe that the Government of India remains highly focused on the education of females through various policies and schemes. For example, the Right of Education Act 2009 made free and compulsory education for children between the ages of six to fourteen years; also, it made it compulsory that a girl child deserves equal opportunity to education as a boy child, according to Mukherjee (2014). Due to this act, the enrolment of school-going girls has been enhanced, resulting in improved literacy of females in the society.

The other glaring program is the "Beti Bachao Beti Padhao" scheme launched in 2015 for female child education. Thus, this scheme has been envisioned to help reverse the condition of the low child-sex ratio prevalent in some states and further the cause of education amongst girls. With a key concentration on awareness programs, community enlightenment, and facilities for girls' education, programs such as "Beti Bachao Beti Padhao" have positively brought change by eradicating the gender divide in education (Mukherjee, 2014).

It is possible to notice that the effect of such initiatives can be seen in numerous spheres of society. Women in general, especially the educated ones, have effectively entered leadership positions on political, economic, and social fronts. Women such as Kiran Mazumdar Shaw, the founder of Biocon Limited, and Dr Indira J Parikh, the founding president of FLAME University, have given impetus to women entrepreneurs in the country's corporate sector and education, respectively (Bapna, 2016). These women show how education prepares women for leadership roles and the resultant impact on the socio-economic status of society.

Furthermore, educated women were notable in transforming society to fight against prejudice and inequality between boys and girls. Traditionally, they act as examples and guides in education for the young, to enter education and various professions. Though they are sportsmen, they engage in social causes, development, and reforms affecting people in their communities. For instance, the female-headed self-help groups have played a remarkable role in enhancing women's education, health, and economic empowerment in the development context of rural women, as aptly pointed out by Pattenden in the year 2011.

Nevertheless, some issues are still observed in questions of gender equality in the education domain, and it is not always possible to provide gender parity. Some of the challenges include culture and economic status; these include socio-economic status and cultural backdrop, and poor infrastructure in the rural setting also posed a major challenge to girl child education. Both problems persist to date, and correcting them requires continued efforts and approaches that foster appropriate conditions for females' education.

WOMEN IN POLITICS

Induction to the political field by women is an important prerequisite for the discharge of their role of charting the vision of Vishwaguru Bharat. Women in Indian politics have come a long way and have set excellent examples from the past for future generations. Some of the well-known leaders are Indira Gandhi, the first female Prime Minister of India. Through such decisions and policies of the leader that she is, her tenure facilitated the enhancement of women's political activity. This contribution of Gandhi can also be convenient to remind the key strategic position, which women can occupy in the decision-making process of nations.

The tradition of Indian women in politics is continued with the present political leaders like Sushma Swaraj, Mamata Banerjee, and many others, and they have played a vital role in the politics of India. Minister of External Affairs Sushma Swaraj had been committed to the welfare of overseas Indians due to the diplomatic brilliance that she was admired for. Mamata Banerjee, the current Chief Minister of West Bengal, has been a well-organized figure in the politics of the state, espousing the causes of social justice and social and economic progress (Kishwar, 1996 p. 303). They have led by example of how able women are to transform the political and social arenas of Indian society.

The Women's Reservation Bill, which seeks to provide for the reserved percentage of seats for women in the Parliament as well as the state legislatures, is a legislative reform aimed at the improvement of women's political representation. This bill intends to examine the low women's representation in the legislative assembly and serve their roles in political leadership (Ghosh, 2009). Despite some of the distortions that the bill has gone through when being passed, it can be seen that the bill holds the key to improving the political status of the country and making it narrow the political gap between males and females.

Women's political involvement can ensure fair representation by the policymakers and, hence, come up with policies that are favorable for all parties. A comparative study conducted among and between sexes showed that women, especially women legislators, are likely to champion social causes, mostly leading to welfare policies that affect larger populations, education, and health (Chattopadhyay & Duflo, 2004). Moreover, by participating in politics, women can contribute appropriate solutions to gender-based issues, appealing for desirable changes that would give women equal rights in the political systems.

Besides portals, women's political parties, and lobbying, women's participation in grassroots organizations and local government is also of the utmost importance for sustainable development. Some of the measures include, for example, the Panchayati Raj institutions, whereby women have been empowered to participate and or be involved in the decision-making process at the grassroots level. Research on women's leadership in these settings has established that women leaders deliver fresh ideas and strategies into the institutions, especially touching on governance, integrated parts of transparency, accountability, and social justice (Buch 2000). Nevertheless, some problems exist regarding the issue of parity of women in the sphere of politics. Socio-cultural factors such as traditions, prejudices, and bias, unresponsive and unfriendly systems combined with poor resource mobilization, improper encouragement, and support networks have remained a push factor to women's political enfranchisement. Solving these challenges involves the initiative to provide support in the organizational environment through capacity building, women as role models for emulation, and formulation of special policies on working conditions for women politicians.

WOMEN IN THE ECONOMY

The economic independence of women is one of the goals in the process of developing the whole economic structure and social conditions in India. Large groups of females work in the informal economy, particularly in agriculture and sales and services, arts and crafts, and small industries. These efforts continue to be unrewarded on both the economic front and in social acknowledgment (Mazumdar, 2004).

Women have succeeded in engaging themselves in the food production cycle from planting to harvesting, especially in the agricultural sector, meaning they are very important in food security in the country. Their work is normally considered marginal, and this overlooks how important this work may be. Likewise, in the handicrafts and small-scale industries, women are managing the traditional products for the arts and crafts business and have evolved ways and means to produce new artifacts that would fit the current market. These industries not only support the cultures and traditions but also are helping Millions of women, especially from the Rural areas (Mazumdar, 2004).

To enable women practitioners in the informal economy to overcome these hurdles and for their overall financial enfranchisement, bringing the micro venture capital along with the SHG movement proves to be path-breaking. The SHG movement has worked quite well in organizing women at the grassroots level and promoting the elements of solidarity. Women at the micro-finance operational SHGs can avail of microcredit, which makes them capable of starting up their businesses and education investment, enhancing the quality of their lives (Pitt et al., 2006).

This paper also adds that microfinance programs also help in increasing women's financial status. Allowed by receiving small amounts of credit secured without collateral, such programs helped women fulfill business initiatives, add sources of income, and in general become more financially independent. The literature review reveals that women's involvement in microfinancing improves their education level, economic status, health, and involvement in decision-making within households (Pitt et al., 2006).

The involvement of women in economic activities is not only helpful for the development of women's personalities but also highly necessary for the integrated development of the country. Women who are financially independent help in the advancement of a country's GDP, decrease poverty, and instigate transformation. For instance, women's social and economic status empowers them to ensure better education and overall health of their offspring, hence producing a better educated and healthier generation in the future (Kabeer, 2001).

Besides, Gender Equality and Women's Economic Empowerment are interconnected and are a part of society's progression. This means if women are economically empowered, they can fully convert and transform inequality practices and policies, and norms, thereby influencing the general society and its norms. This also empowers the women politically since the economic independence of the women leads them to engage in activities such as leadership and politics more often than their less empowered counterparts.

However, existing problems are not eradicated, and they are the following to sum up, the problems of injected poverty, unemployment, and social helplessness are still present even though there are certain efforts made through the formation of SHGs

and microfinance practices. Several challenges affect women in the informal segment, including credit accessibility constraints, low market access, and other factors, including inadequate training and consultancy services. To solve these problems, suitable and wide-ranging policies aimed at ensuring the right to education, training, and financial education. Similarly, the development of legal instruments that enhance women's rights to work and end discrimination in the workplace cannot be ignored.

CULTURAL CONTRIBUTIONS

Finally, the social role of Indian women has been remarkable in being the conveyor of tradition and a change-maker in the cultural endowment of India. They have made their valuable writings in literature, music, dancing, and another gross field, which shows that Indian society is not only static but has also vibrated with the scull of arts. Over time, starting from the pre-historic to the contemporary ages, Indian women have enjoyed the status of being carriers of culture and change.

Indian women in literature have written works that were culturally relevant to the context and, at the same time, broke new ground in terms of the stories and formats. Some of the current popular writers of India are Arundhati Roy, who has written 'the god of Small Things' and Anita Desai who has written 'Clear Light of Day'. The God of Small Things by Arundhati Roy is the Booker Prize winner of 1997, where a profound view of social questions and people's bonds in India is depicted. Likewise, Desai's novels, like Clear Light of Day and In Custody, present a sensitive picture of Indian society and deal with the themes of tradition and modernity in Indian culture (Dhawan, 2005). These writers enlighten people not only on the variety of Indian literature but also on the problems of Indian women that concern the whole world.

Speaking of the talents in the sphere of music and dancing, the position of Indian women can be described as rather high, as they are famous performers, teachers, and even creators. Renowned personalities like Rukmini Devi Arundale and Yamini Krishnamurthy are the starters who have made a lot of effort to reemerge and promote Bharatanatyam, a classical dance form, and Shubha Mudgal and Kishori Amonkar have contributed a lot to Indian classical music. It is due to such artists that the traditional forms have been maintained and incorporated with innovations to fit into modern worlds (Vatsyayan 1997).

Women have not been left behind when it comes to creating the visual arts. This is because contemporary artists such as Amrita Sher-Gil and Anjolie Ela Menon have brought in pretty strong points in the forms and content of their artworks. For example, the subjects of Sher-Gil's compositions are frequently Indian women and their mundane lives – all this is done to question the existing order and to present the critical position of an Indian woman. Basic to Menon's art are bright colors and distorted forms; this creates the impact of Indian and Western styles, signaling the mixture of the old and new (Mago,2000).

In this context, the participation of women in cultural conservation and creation extends a harmonious identity to India as Vishwaguru Bharat. These representations regarding women assist in upholding culture but at the same time being modern and aligning with the existing structure of the Indian society. Thus, preserving the age-old customs and enforcing innovations, women guarantee that Indians' traditions remain spirited and alive.

Moreover, women's engagement in cultural practices promotes social cohesion as people experience themselves as belonging to more collectivity. They demonstrate the various forms of cultures that exist in India, hence supporting social inclusion and the unity of the nation. The cultural narratives that are built by the female narrators reflect issues of gender and culture, and individual and collective identity as well as resistance, hence are part of social justice discourses on gender and social equity.

Still, issues persist, even though these achievements are noteworthy; sadly, women in the arts face much discrimination and, as such, are not accorded many opportunities just like their male counterparts. To address some of these problems, there is a need to develop a better environment that will favor the participation of females in the cultural fields, besides providing policies that will enhance such participation. Fresh opportunities and support programs in terms of finance, training, as well as visibility can contribute to the emergence of women artists and cultural workers.

The many challenges facing ASCT let us consider how, within a decade, it might consolidate its status as a strong actor on the international development scene that can offer quality educational opportunities through cooperation with international partners.

There has been a slow but steady improvement in women's rights in India; however, women face a myriad of challenges that limit their opportunities and total liberation. Such obstacles as prejudice against women, abuse, and restricted opportunities require a more extensive approach, including policy measures and a change in people's perception to ensure equal rights for women (Desai & Thakkar, 2001).

Ending discrimination based on gender has not been effectively practiced in different forms of employment and is still present in sectors that continue to pay women less than their male counterparts, offer a minimal chance at career progression, and perpetuate patriarchy by restricting women's duties to their domestic responsibilities. Even where this discrimination occurs, it is an indoctrinated prejudice located in parts of culture and society, hence making it hard to eliminate. For example, the women in the workforce earn less wages and are barred by the glass ceilings, and thereby they lack economic power and promotions (Desai & Thakkar, 2001).

Violence against women is another calamitous problem that increases the risks of threatening women's lives. Woman endangerment is a prevalent issue in a society where the ladies of all classes are in one way or another affected by domestic violence, sexual harassment, or other forms of gender-based violence. The legal framework comprises several laws like the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act should have been acted on and prevented in 2005 and rigid penalties regarding sexual harassment however; these laws are practiced and enforced inadequately and thus require better functioning procedures and basic social awareness to halt such crimes (Desai & Thakkar, 2001).

Lack of restricted availability to things such as education, medical sections, and timely financial assistance also complicates the situation for women. Inadequate educational facilities, unique to rural settings, limit women's literacy and limit their chances of progressing to universities or acquiring a professional job. A major issue is healthcare, with many women currently unable to access proper maternal and reproductive health services, and as a result, there are high incidences of maternal mortality and poor health (Sen & Ostlin, 2008).

All these issues have no easy solutions and can be managed only through the help of an interdisciplinary approach. Educating girls to end gender prejudices is key. It would also be relevant to point out that guaranteeing girls' access to quality education from the earliest stages in particular can create the foundation for girls' empowerment. Measures such as implementing changes in educational systems that involve gender-sensitive curricula and focusing on engaging more females in STEM are some of the ways that can free women from gender roles (Kabeer, 2005).

Likewise, legal changes are also imperative contributing to the enhancement of women's rights and their social enfranchisement. The improvement in the enactment of the existing laws, as well as the formulation of new legislation, may help in offering a more secure environment for women. For example, appropriate legislation, which includes the provision of equal wages for equal work, and positive discrimination legislation in Favor of work/family reconciliation, as the legislation that supports the demand for maternity leave and childcare, can improve women's employment opportunities (Kabeer, 2005).

This paper establishes that economic opportunities are important in supporting women's full realization of equality. Crediting and insurance help women open businesses and stimulate economic growth, thus granting them access to financial services can help them access credit. It is therefore important to empower women through microfinancing, business management entrepreneurial training in as regards to marketplace productivity (Pitt et al., 2006). Also, promoting employment of women in the formal economy and proper protection of women in the informal economy will help to implement better efficiency into the notions of economic participation.

Therefore, achieving the concept of a women-friendly environment that is conducive to the leadership of women requires policy solutions and cultural transformation. When the media as well as local community programs and public campaigns are used responsibly, it becomes possible to challenge and change the existing stereotypical gender norms. Including men in gender equality activities can also help transform social cultures; an essential precondition of which is the encouragement of male support in activities supporting gender equality (Cornwall, 2016).

CONCLUSION

Vishwaguru Bharat's strategic functioning cannot be fully realized without the active participation of women. Women have been core to the socio-economic development of India historically and in the current globalized world educating, participating in politics, supporting the economy, and inspiring culture.

For the education sector, the innovations brought by various government policies as well as change in society have uplifted women to act as agents of change within their societies hence nurturing equality. The presence of women in politics as exhibited by female leaders and bills such as the Women's Reservation Bill is important to ensure that policies being formulated are more gender sensitive.

Women's economic inclusion, particularly through SGH movement and micro finance is critical to the growth of India and to support status of women so that they can effectively participate in the economy. Women, in Indian culture, have strengthened the country's history to be encompassed through the treasury of literature, music, dance, and art while exhibiting more tradition than modernity.

Nevertheless, the following are some of the achievements; despite the progress made on these, the new challenges seen include gender violence, discrimination, and inadequate resource control. Solving these problems implies the need to take extensive measures at the policy level and legislative and cultural amendments. It implies that enhancing the status of women and their engagement across different domains of society is crucial to attaining the develop-India dream of making India Vishwaguru Bharat, based on equitable growth.

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Author Profile: Kumari Pooja Anand is a Ph.D. Scholar at the Department of Psychology, Patliputra University. Primarily Ms Anand works in the area of mental health of working and non-working women. Ms Anand has four years of experience as a clinical psychologist. She has specialization also in treating mental illness such as anxiety, depression, PTSD, and OCD. Additionally, she has co-authored a book titled “**Beyond the Limits,**” which offers accessible insights into overcoming various challenges.